

Hydration of Belite-Ye'elimite-Ferrite cements: thermodynamic modeling

LOTTHENBACH Barbara¹, ALBERT Blandine², MORIN Vincent², GARTNER Ellis²

1. Laboratory for Concrete / Construction Chemistry, Empa, Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology, 8600 Dübendorf, Switzerland
2. Lafarge Research Center, Process & Environment Program, 38291 Saint Quentin Fallavier, France

Abstract

This paper describes a study of the hydration of belite-ye'elimite ferrite (BYF) cements, made from clinkers comprising principally belite (C_2S), with ye'elimite (C_4A_3S) and ferrite (C_4AF) as the two main secondary phases, and inter-ground with calcium sulfates. The clinkers used in this study also contained some boron in order to stabilize α' - C_2S at room temperature. The main hydration products of these cements at early ages are the same as the products of ye'elimite hydration in presence of calcium sulfate: ettringite, calcium monosulfoaluminate, and aluminum hydroxide. At later ages, this initial product assemblage is modified by the hydration of the belite and ferrite phases, producing strätlingite, siliceous hydrogarnet and C-S-H, while aluminum hydroxide is consumed. The changes in the phase assemblage during hydration were calculated by thermodynamic modeling based on the cement database CEMDATA07 updated with recent data on siliceous hydrogarnets. Thermodynamic calculations were carried out using the GEMS approach for BYF cements with high and low ye'elimite content and compared to the experimental data obtained by XRD and TGA. The equilibrium predictions matched well with the experimental results at longer reaction times. However, at early reaction times the phase assemblage obtained is strongly influenced by kinetics.

Originality

Modeling of hydration process of belite-ye'elimite-ferrite cements has not been published up to now (only modeling of typical calcium sulfoaluminate cement).

Use of updated thermodynamic database for cements.

Comparison with experimental data for clinkers with varying compositions.

Keywords:

Thermodynamic calculations; Hydration; Belite-Ye'elimite-Ferrite cements; siliceous hydrogarnets.

² Corresponding author: blandine.albert@lafarge.com, Tel +33-474 821 607, Fax +33-474 168 0

1. Introduction

Concrete is the most widely used man-made material. Portland Cement clinker (PCC) is the most important active ingredient in almost all construction concretes, its hydration providing strength and durability. However, PCC production is associated with a high CO₂ release (typically about 0.9 tons of CO₂ per ton of PCC, of which about 60% is “fossil” CO₂ resulting from decarbonation of limestone in the raw materials). One approach to reducing CO₂ emissions is to reduce the proportion of limestone in the raw materials, giving clinker composition lower in calcium, such as, for example, belite rich clinkers. In order to compensate for the lower reactivity of belite relative to alite, and further reduce the calcium content, it is also advantageous to replace the tri-calcium aluminate phase (C₃A) with ye’elimite (C₄A₃F), thus obtaining a Belite-Ye’elimite-Ferrite (BYF) clinker. (Gartner E.M., 2011). These clinkers can be used to make cements in the usual way, by intergrinding with a source of calcium sulfate, and Supplementary Cementing Materials (SCMs) such as slag or fly ash can also be added. The resulting cements are generally outside the range of the Chinese CSA (Third Cement Series) cements, as the ye’elimite content is less than 35%.

The feasibility of industrial-scale production of BYF cements has been demonstrated at two cement plants (Gartner E.M., *et al.*, 2014). In-situ measurements confirmed CO₂ savings between 25 and 30%. These cements have been used to make different types of concrete for testing (Quillin K., *et al.*, 2014). The results of mechanical and durability tests showed that the usage properties of these new cements are very close to those of OPC.

However, the hydration path of BYF cements is different from that of OPC, as detailed in a number of previous studies (Li G., *et al.*, 2007; Wang J., *et al.*, 2010; Morin V., *et al.*, 2011). The goal of the present study is to determine how closely the observed hydrated phase assemblage at any given degree of hydration follows the composition predicted by thermodynamic equilibrium (ignoring the anhydrous phases).

2. Materials and Methods

Neat paste samples were prepared from different BYF cements, and analyzed quantitatively to follow changes in their phase assemblage from one day to one year of hydration at 20°C. Thermodynamic calculations were run using GEMS software with an updated database, and the calculated results are compared to the experimental results.

The materials and methods are described in detail in the article of Morin V., *et al.*, 2015 of this ICCO edition. The main aspects are briefly summarized in the subsequent sections.

2.1. Cements

Two cements are investigated in this study, designated as “Cement A” and “Cement B”. Cement A is relatively rich in ye’elimite, while B shows higher content of belite and ferrite, and a relatively low content of ye’elimite (see table 1).

Table 1 Cements A and B – Rietveld quantitative phase analysis results

Weight %	Ye’elimite	Belite	Ferrite	Anhydrite	Hemi-hydrate	Other phases
Cement A	31	36	13	8	2	10
Cement B	14	53	21	10	0	2

The ferrite composition corresponds to C₄A_{0.67}F_{1.33}. Belite includes two types of C₂S, beta-C₂S and alpha’-C₂S. The alpha’ form of C₂S is stabilized due to the presence of boron (1.38%

B₂O₃ in both clinkers). In addition, some minor phases were present, which were considered as inert. Other characteristics of the cements are given in table 2. The specific Blaine surface was measured according to the European standard EN 196-6. The flexural and compressive strengths were measured with 4 x 4 x 16 cm prism mortar specimen with a cement/sand/water ratio of 1:3:0.5, and cured at 20°C, 95 +/-5%, according to the standard EN 196-1.

Table 2 Cements A and B - Physical and mechanical properties

	Specific surface (m ² /kg)	Flexural strength (MPa)		Compressive strength (MPa)	
		1d	28d	1d	28d
Cement A	420	4.5	7.2	25	56
Cement B	400	2.7	5.5	11.7	39

2.2. Preparation of paste specimens

Paste specimens were mixed at a water/cement mass ratio (w/c) of 0.67 for the cement A and 0.50 for the cement B (a higher w/c was chosen for cement A to avoid a lack of water during hydration of this cement which contains more ye'elimite). Specimens were cured at 20°C. Hydration was stopped after different hydration times (from one day to one year) by crushing the hydrated paste and remove the free water by washing with acetone and diethyl ether.

2.3. Analysis of neat paste specimens

Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) were carried out to get the amount of the structurally bound water, i.e. the mass loss between 50 and 550°C (%weightloss [50-550°C]). The analyses were carried out in a N₂ atmosphere on about 100 mg of sample at a heating rate of 10°C/minute until 1000°C. The apparatus is a SETARAM TG-DTA 92-16.

X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) measurements were carried out using CuK α radiation on a PANalytical X'Pert Pro diffractometer in a θ -2 θ configuration with an angular scan 5°-65° (2 θ) and an X'Celerator detector. The amount of phases was quantified using a dedicated Rietveld calculation file as detailed in Morin V., *et al.*, 2015.

The combination of TGA and XRD data leads to the determination of the amount of residual anhydrous phases and the precipitated hydrated phases. The amount per mass of sample is evaluated using Rietveld calculations (%X_{/100g of sample}) expressed as a function of the initial dry cement using the relationship: %X_{/100g dry cement} = %X_{/100g of sample} x 100 / (100 - (%weightloss [50-550°C]))

3. Modeling

Thermodynamic modeling was carried out using the geochemical software GEMS (Gibbs Energy Minimization Software for Thermodynamic Modeling; Kulik D.A. *et al.*, 2013). This software has been used successfully to simulate the hydration of Portland cement pastes (Lothenbach B., Winnefeld F., 2006) (Lothenbach B., Wieland E., 2006), Chinese calcium sulfoaluminate cements (Winnefeld F., Lothenbach B., 2010), and mixes of PC and CSA cements (Pelletier L., *et al.*, 2010, 2011).

For this study, the PSI-Nagra thermodynamic database (Hummel W., *et al.*, 2002; Thoenen T., *et al.*, 2003) was coupled with a cement-specific database CEMDATA07 (Lothenbach B., *et al.*, 2008, Matschei T., *et al.*, 2007), updated with recent thermodynamic data for katoite (Lothenbach B., *et al.*, 2012), iron containing hydrates (Dilnesa B.Z., *et al.*, 2011, 2012, 2014a, 2014b) and C-S-H (Kulik D.A., 2011). To account for the presence of borate, the thermodynamic data for aqueous boron species and for B-AFm and B-AFt from Champenois J.-P., *et al.* (2015) were also implemented, as summarized in Table 7.

All calculations were done for systems at 20°C under oxidizing conditions (air). As input data, the measured amounts of the initial cement phases reacted (ye'elimite, belite, ferrite, the different forms of initial calcium sulfate) after different reaction times were used. The amount of borate reacted was related to the reaction of belite as previous experiments (Wang J., 2010) showed that approximately 95% of boron is associated with belite. The formation of crystalline iron and aluminum (hydr-)oxides (hematite, magnetite, gibbsite and $C_3AS_{0.41}H_{5.18}$) was suppressed during the calculations as these phases do not precipitate readily at room temperature (Dilnesa B.Z., et al., 2014a). The Al/Fe ratio in $C_3(A,F)S_{0.84}H_{4.32}$ was limited to ≤ 1 , based on the Al/Fe ratio observed in Portland cements hydrated for 2 years or longer (Dilnesa B.Z., et al., 2014b).

4. Results

4.1. Experimental results for cement A

The amounts of residual anhydrous phases and precipitated hydrates phases are given in the table below. No hemihydrate was detected after 1 day, but there was some residual anhydrite. The term “Ms” corresponds to calcium monosulfoaluminate and “Si-Hg” the sum of the low- and high siliceous hydrogarnets analyzed by XRD as detailed in Morin *et al.*, 2015.

Table 3 Phases quantification for hydrated neat paste made with cement A and w/c=0.67;
Experimental results (g/100g of dry cement).

Wt%	Ye'elimite	Belite	Ferrite	Anhydrite	Ettringite	Ms	Al(OH) ₃	Straetlingite	Si-Hg	C-S-H
1d	0	34	11	2.5	51	5.1	22	0	0	0
7d	0	25	7.2	2.5	47	7.2	5.8	36	0.9	0
14d	0	14	4.3	0.8	53	9.7	0	49	9.1	0
28d	0	11	0	0	57	9.4	0	54	9.7	0
91d	0	6	0	0	56	14	0	48	17	2.7
180d	0	4	0	0	58	16	0	39	21	6
365d	0	4	0	0	63	11	0	31	29	7

The main hydration products of BYF cements at early ages are the same as the products of ye'elimite hydration in presence of calcium sulfate: ettringite, calcium monosulfoaluminate, and aluminum hydroxide. At later ages, this initial product assemblage is modified by the hydration of the belite and ferrite phases, resulting in the formation of straetlingite, siliceous hydrogarnets and C-S-H, while aluminum hydroxide is consumed.

The fractions of reacted ye'elimite, belite, ferrite and anhydrite for cement A are plotted in figure 1.

Figure 1 Hydration degree of the main cement phases (cement A, w/c=0.67)

Ye'elinite reacts very fast and is consumed within 1 day of hydration. The reaction of the calcium sulfate is slightly slower, as often observed for natural anhydrite. The significant mechanical strengths measured at early age (one day) are thus due to the hydration of ye'elinite and calcium sulfate. Ferrite and belite started to react significantly between one and seven days of hydration contributing to the late strength. After ninety-one days, ferrite has completely reacted while the hydration degree of belite reaches a maximum value of 88%. The global hydration degree of the cement well above 90% can be considered as very satisfying after three months of hydration at 20°C.

4.2. Thermodynamic calculations for cement A

As mentioned above, as input for the calculations the amount of clinker that had reacted at each time step was used. The composition of the phase assemblages calculated with GEMS for the different times is given in the table 4 below.

Table 4 Phases quantification for hydrated neat paste made with cement A and w/c=0.67; GEMS results (g/100g of dry cement).

Wt%	Ettringite	Boro-AFt	Ms	Al(OH) ₃	Straetlingite	C-S-H	C ₃ (A _{0.5} F _{0.5})S _{0.84} H _{4.32}
1d	47	1.2	6.5	15	0	0	6
7d	60	4	0	0	20.3	0	12
14d	60	5.4	0	0	33	0	19
28d	60	9	0	0	36	2.7	24
91d	60	12	0	0	35	7.4	27
180d	60	12	0	0	35	8.3	27
365d	60	12	0	0	35	8.3	27

For a better visualization for the changes during hydration, the amounts of phases are converted in volumes using the molar volume of each phase (see values in Appendix). The volumes are expressed in cm³ per 100 grams of initial dry cement in figure 2b and the calculations are compared with the volumes obtained experimentally (figure 2a). Note that “Ettringite” and “B-AFt” are put together in figure 2b, as these are very difficult to distinguish experimentally.

Similar to the experimental observations, the calculations predict initially the formation of ettringite, aluminum hydroxide and some monosulfate. Aluminum hydroxide dissolves and straetlingite is formed as the reaction of belite supplies CaO and SiO₂:

As ferrite reacts, it leads to the formation of siliceous hydrogarnet. In the calculations monosulfate AFm converts completely to ettringite and siliceous hydrogarnet after 1 week according to:

while in the experiments this transformation seems kinetically hindered and monosulfate persists up to 1 year. This kinetic hindrance of hydrogarnet formation is experimentally observed in Portland cements (e.g. Dilnesa B., *et al.*, 2014a) and seems to occur also in CSA containing systems.

Figure 2 Evolution of the mineralogical composition of neat paste (cement A, w/c=0.67, experiments (a) and modeling (b))

4.3. Experimental results for cement B

The same modeling approach was applied for cement B, resulting in the hydrate compositions given in Table 5.

Table 5 Phases quantification for hydrated neat paste made with cement B and w/c=0.50; Experimental results (g/100g of dry cement).

wt%	Ye'elimite	Belite	Ferrite	Anhydrite	Ettringite	Ms	Al(OH) ₃	Straetlingite	Si-Hg	C-S-H
1d	0	50	13	0	46	0	13	0	0	0
7d	0	35	3.4	0	50	0	0	24	14	0
14d	0	35	3.4	0	49	0	0	24	16	3
28d	0	26	3.4	0	52	0	0	14	19	15
56d	0	16	2.4	0	43	11	0	3.3	20	37
91d	0	14	2.4	0	44	15	0	1.1	23	35
180d	0	9.5	2.4	0	41	15	0	0	8.9	42

Again, the main hydration products at early ages are ettringite and aluminum hydroxide. After one week and longer, this initial product assemblage is modified due to the hydration of the belite and ferrite phases, and straetlingite, siliceous hydrogarnet and C-S-H are formed, while aluminum hydroxide is consumed. The main difference to cement A is the presence of less straetlingite and the higher siliceous hydrogarnet content, which is related to the higher ferrite content of cement B. After two weeks, the straetlingite content is diminished, and it completely disappears after three months, while the amounts of siliceous-hydrogarnet and C-S-H increases. After one year of hydration, the main hydration products are ettringite, C-S-H, siliceous hydrogarnet and monosulfate.

The degree of reaction of the clinker phases vs. time is plotted in figure 3.

Figure 3 Hydration degree of the main cement phases (cement B, w/c=0.50)

As for cement A, ye'elimite and anhydrite react very fast: both have completely reacted by one day. The reaction of ferrite is somewhat faster than what was observed for cement A, a hydration degree of 80% being reached after 14 days. Belite started to react between one and seven days to reach a reaction degree of 51% after 28 days and 89% after one year of hydration.

4.4. Thermodynamic calculations for cement B

Again, the amount of reacted clinker was used as input for the calculations. The composition of the phase assemblages calculated with GEMS at each time is given in the table 6 and compared with the experimental findings in figure 4.

Table 6 Phases quantification for hydrated neat paste made with cement B and w/c=0.50; GEMS results (g/100g of dry cement).

Wt%	Ettringite	B-AFt	Ms	Al(OH) ₃	Straetlingite	C-S-H	C ₃ (A _{0.5} F _{0.5})S _{0.84} H _{4.32}
1d	40	0.1	0	6.6	0	0	9.4
7d	40	0.1	0	1.4	7.2	0	30
14d	40	3.6	0	0	8	5	35
28d	37	5.8	3.7	0	5.1	15	37
56d	35	7.1	8.6	0	2.1	23	38
91d	33	8	11	0	0.4	28	39
180d	33	9	11	0	0	34	39
365d	34	9.7	11	0	0	38	40

As for cement A, generally a good agreement between calculated and experimental values is

observed.

Figure 4 Evolution of the mineralogical composition of neat paste made with cement B and $w/c=0.50$ (experiments (a) and modeling (b))

5. Discussion

For both BYF cements studied there is a very good agreement between the experimentally determined and modeled compositions of the hydrated pastes. This agreement was improved by limiting the amount of aluminum in the siliceous hydrogarnet $C_3(A,F)S_{0.84}H_{4.34}$. This assumption was inspired from the recent work of Dilnesa et al. on the characteristics of siliceous hydrogarnet in hydrated PC paste. Nevertheless, there are still some small differences between experiments and modeling: straelingite content is under-estimated and

therefore siliceous hydrogarnet over-estimated. This may be due to the fact that siliceous hydrogarnet will form only slowly at room temperature. Researchers working on these phases usually carried out their experiment around 95 or 105°C under atmospheric atmosphere to obtain siliceous hydrogarnet in reasonable time (e.g. Dilnesa B., *et al.*, 2014a; Matschei T., *et al.*, 2007; Jappy T.G., Glasser F.P., 1991).

A comparison of the solid hydrated volume observed and calculated after 1 year shows a significantly higher total volume for the ye'elimite rich cement A (about 72cm³/100g) than for cement B (62cm³/100g). The higher hydrated volume for cement A compared to cement B presumably explains the higher compressive strength obtained for cement A, (see table 2).

6. Conclusions

Modeling of the hydration pathway of Belite-Ye'elimite-Ferrite cements was successfully carried out with GEMS: the hydrated phase assemblages predicted matched well with the experimental results obtained with two different cements hydrated for over one year at 20°C. This agreement was possible thanks to the recent determination of thermodynamic data for siliceous hydrogarnet and the boron containing phases B-AFt and B-AFm. However, we had to restrict the aluminum content of siliceous hydrogarnet to what has previously been observed for hydrated PC pastes. Thermodynamic calculations nevertheless underestimated straeltingite content and consequently siliceous hydrogarnet content. This relatively small discrepancy can be attributed to kinetic hindrance of siliceous hydrogarnet formation at room temperature. The results here suggest that the thermodynamic approach should also be helpful for further modeling of both mechanical and durability-related properties.

7. Appendix

Table 7 Thermodynamic data for hydrogarnet, AH₃, FH₃, AFm and AFt phases at 25°C and 1 atm.

	log K _{S0}	volume [cm ³ /mol]	References
<hr/>			
Katoite: $Ca_3Al_2(OH)_{12} \Leftrightarrow 3Ca^{2+} + 2Al(OH)_4^- + 4OH^-$	-20.50	150	(Lothenbach B., <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
$Ca_3Al_2(SiO_4)_{0.84}(OH)_{8.64} \Leftrightarrow 3Ca^{2+} + 2Al(OH)_4^- + 0.84 SiO(OH)_3^- + 3.16OH^- - 2.52H_2O$	-26.70	142	(Dilnesa B., <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
$Ca_3Fe_2(OH)_{12} \Leftrightarrow 3Ca^{2+} + 2Fe(OH)_4^- + 4OH^-$	-26.30	155	(Dilnesa B., <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
$Ca_3Fe_2(SiO_4)_{0.84}(OH)_{8.64} \Leftrightarrow 3Ca^{2+} + 2Fe(OH)_4^- + 0.84 SiO(OH)_3^- + 3.16OH^- - 2.52H_2O$	-32.50	149	(Dilnesa B., <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
$Ca_3Fe_2(SiO_4)_{1.34}(OH)_{6.64} \Leftrightarrow 3Ca^{2+} + 2Fe(OH)_4^- + 1.34SiO(OH)_3^- + 2.66OH^- - 4.02H_2O$	-34.20	145	(Dilnesa B., <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
Ettringite: $Ca_6Al_2(SO_4)_3(OH)_{12} \cdot 26H_2O \Leftrightarrow 6Ca^{2+} + 2Al(OH)_4^- + 3SO_4^{2-} + 4OH^- + 26H_2O$	-44.9	707	(Lothenbach B., <i>et al.</i> , 2008)
Fe-ettringite: $Ca_6Fe_2(SO_4)_3(OH)_{12} \cdot 26H_2O \Leftrightarrow 6Ca^{2+} + 2Fe(OH)_4^- + 3SO_4^{2-} + 4OH^- + 26H_2O$	-44.0	717	(Lothenbach B., <i>et al.</i> , 2008)
B-AFt: $Ca_6Al_2(BO_3)_4(OH)_{14} \cdot 26H_2O \Leftrightarrow 6Ca^{2+} + 2Al(OH)_4^- + 4B(OH)_4^- + 6OH^- + 18H_2O$	-42.92	679	(Champenois J.-B., <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
Monosulfate: $Ca_4Al_2(SO_4)(OH)_{12} \cdot 6H_2O \Leftrightarrow 4Ca^{2+} + 2Al(OH)_4^- + SO_4^{2-} + 4OH^- + 6H_2O$	-29.26	309	(Matschei T., <i>et al.</i> , 2008)

Fe-monosulfate: $Ca_4Fe_2(SO_4)(OH)_{12} \cdot 6H_2O$	$\Leftrightarrow 4Ca^{2+} + 2Fe(OH)_4^- + SO_4^{2-} + 4OH^- + 6H_2O$	
-31.57	321	(Dilnesa B., <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
B-AFm: $Ca_4Al_2(BO_2)(OH)_{13} \cdot 6.28H_2O$	$\Leftrightarrow 4Ca^{2+} + 2Al(OH)_4^- + B(OH)_4^- + 5OH^- + 6.28H_2O$	
-29.17	287	(Champenois J.-B., <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
Straetlingite: $Ca_2Al_2SiO_2(OH)_{10} \cdot 3H_2O$	$\Leftrightarrow 2Ca^{2+} + 2Al(OH)_4^- + SiO(OH)_3^- + 2OH^- + 3H_2O$	
-19.70	216	(Matschei T., <i>et al.</i> , 2008)
$Al(OH)_{3,mic} + H_2O$	$\Leftrightarrow Al(OH)_4^- - OH^-$	
-0.67	32	(Lothenbach B., <i>et al.</i> , 2012)
$Fe(OH)_{3,am} + H_2O$	$\Leftrightarrow Fe(OH)_4^- - OH^-$	
-4.6	34	(Lothenbach B., <i>et al.</i> , 2008)

8. References

- Champenois, J.-B., Dhoury, M., Cau Dit Coumes, C., Mercier, C., Revel, B., Le Bescop, P., Damidot, D., 2015. Influence of sodium borate on the early age hydration of calcium sulfoaluminate cement. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 70, 83-93.
- Dilnesa B.Z., Lothenbach B., Le Saout G., Renaudin G., Mesbah A., Filinchuk Y., Wichser A., Wieland E., 2011. Iron in carbonate containing AFm phases. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 41, 311-323.
- Dilnesa B.Z., Lothenbach B., Renaudin G., Wichser A., Wieland E., 2012. Stability of monosulfate in the presence of iron, *Journal of the American Ceramic Society* 95, 3305-3316.
- Dilnesa B.Z., Lothenbach B., Renaudin G., Wichser A., Kulik D., 2014a. Synthesis and characterization of hydrogarnet $Ca_3(Al_xFe_{1-x})_2(SiO_4)_y(OH)_{4(3-y)}$. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 59, 96-111.
- Dilnesa B.Z., Wieland E., Lothenbach B., Dähn R., Scrivener K., 2014b. Fe-containing phases in hydrated cements, *Cement and Concrete Research*, 58, 45-55
- Gartner E.M., Macphee D.E., 2011. A physico-chemical basis for novel cementitious binders. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 41, 736-749.
- Gartner E.M., Comparet C., Albert B., Dunster A. M., 2014. Project Aether. *International Cement Review*, September, 1067-107.
- Hummel W., Berner U., Curti E., Pearson F.J., Thoenen T., 2002. Nagra/PSI Chemical Thermodynamic Data Base 01/01, Universal Publishers/uPUBLISH.com, USA, Also Published as Nagra Technical Report NTB 02-16, Wetingen, Switzerland.
- Kulik D.A., 2011. Improving the structural consistency of C-S-H solid solution thermodynamic models. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 41, 477-495.
- Kulik D.A., Wagner T., Dmytrieva S.V., Kosakowski, G., Hingerl, F.F., Chudnenko, K.V., Berner, U. 2013. GEM-Selektor geochemical modeling package: revised algorithm and GEMS3K numerical kernel for coupled simulation codes. *Computational Geosciences*, 17(1), 1-24.
- Jappy T.G., Glasser F.P., 1991. Synthesis and stability of silica-substituted hydrogarnet $Ca_3Al_2Si_{3-x}O_{12-4x}(OH)_{4x}$. *Advances in Cement Research*, 4, No. 1, 1-8.
- Li G.S., Walenta G., Gartner E.M., 2007. Formation and Hydration of Low-CO₂ Cement based on Belite, Calcium Sulfoaluminate and Calcium Aluminoferrite. In: Proceedings of the 12th International Congress on the Chemistry of Cements, Montreal.

- Lothenbach B., Winnefeld F., 2006. Thermodynamic modelling of the hydration of Portland cement. *Cement Concrete Research*, 36, 209–226.
- Lothenbach B., Wieland E., 2006. A thermodynamic approach to the hydration of sulphate-resisting Portland cement. *Waste Management*, 26, 706-719.
- Lothenbach B., Matschei T., Möschner G., et al., 2008. Thermodynamic modelling of the effect of temperature on the hydration and porosity of Portland cement. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 38(1), 1-18.
- Lothenbach B., Pelletier-Chaignat L., Winnefeld F., 2012. Stability in the system CaO-Al₂O₃-H₂O, *Cement and Concrete Research*, 42, 1621-1634.
- Matschei T., Lothenbach B. and Glasser F., 2007. Thermodynamic properties of Portland cement hydrates in the system CaO-Al₂O₃-SiO₂-CaSO₄-CaCO₃-H₂O. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 37(10), 1379-1410.
- Morin V., Walenta G., Gartner E. M., Termkhajornkit P., Baco I., Casabonne J. M.. Hydration of a Belite-Calcium Sulfoaluminate-Ferrite cement: Aether™, In: Ángel Palomo, Aniceto Zaragoza and Juan Carlos López Agüí, ed. 13th International Congress on the Chemistry of Cement, Madrid 3-8 July 2011.
- Morin V., Baco I., Termkhajornkit P., Albert B., 2015. Impact of calcium sulfate addition on the hydration of belite phase in Belite-Ye'elimite-Ferrite cement. 15th International Congress on the Chemistry of Cement, Beijing 13-16 October 2015.
- Pelletier L., Winnefeld F., Lothenbach B., 2010. The ternary system Portland cement – calcium sulfoaluminate clinker – anhydrite: hydration mechanism and mortar properties. *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 32, 497–507.
- Pelletier, L., Winnefeld, F., Lothenbach, B., Le Saout, G., Müller, C.J., Famy, C. (2011) Influence of calcium sulphate source on the hydration mechanism of Portland cement - calcium sulfoaluminate clinker – calcium sulphate binders. *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 33, 551-561.
- Quillin K.C., Dunster A.M., Tipple C., Walenta G., Gartner E., Albert B., 2014. Project Aether: Testing the durability of a lower-CO₂ alternative to Portland cement. *34th Cement and Concrete Science Conference*, Paper Number 142, 14-17 September 2014, University of Sheffield.
- Thoenen T., Kulik D., 2003. Nagra/PSI Chemical Thermodynamic Database 01/01 for the GEM-Selektor (V.2-PSI) Geochemical Modeling Code, PSI, Villigen, available at <http://les.web.psi.ch/Software/GEMSPSI/doc/pdf/TM-44-03-04-web.pdf>.
- Wang J., Baco I., Morin V., Walenta G., Damidot D., Gartner E.M., 2010. Hydration Mechanisms of Cement Based on Low CO₂ Clinkers Containing Belite, Ye'elimite and Calcium Alumino-Ferrite, In: Proceedings of the 7th International Symposium on Cement and Concrete (ISCC 2010), Jinan, China, May 9–12, 2010ISCC, 2010.
- Wang J., 2010. *Hydration mechanism of cements based on low-CO₂ clinkers containing belite, ye'elimite and calcium alumino-ferrite*. Thesis (PhD). University of Lille.
- Winnefeld, F., Lothenbach, B. (2010) Hydration of calcium sulfoaluminate cements – experimental findings and thermodynamic modelling. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 40, 1239-1247.